

LATE COMPLICATIONS AFTER DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITER OPERATIONS: A RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF POSTOPERATIVE HYPOTHYROIDISM AND RECURRENCE

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Abstract. *Relevance and necessity of the topic. Researchers have reported that hypoparathyroidism (6-20%) and laryngeal nerve damage (2-10%) are lower after subtotal thyroid resection compared with thyroidectomy [3]. There is temporary and permanent hypoparathyroidism (stops before and after 6 months, respectively). Persistent hypoparathyroidism develops as a result of surgical trauma, removal of the parathyroid glands, or involvement in the scar adhesion process. Low levels of calcium and vitamin D and aging play an important role in the development of transient hypoparathyroidism [1].*

In evaluating the results of operative treatment of DTG, attention is paid to recurrent disease, laryngeal nerve damage, hypocalcemia, hypothyroidism, and hyperparathyroidism [2]. For DTG, the Russian Association of Endocrinologists recommends thyroidectomy (TE), which often develops various specific complications in the postoperative period. [4;5;6;7].

Keywords: *gland autograft, trauma, removal of the parathyroid glands, histomorphological assessment, ST examination.*

The aim of the scientific research. Improvement of operative treatment of DTG patients, regulation of thyroid function, study of hormonal and stimulatory antibodies, allowing revision of histomorphological assessment, study and improvement of these results in morning and evening complications.

Research materials. 263 patients who underwent surgery for diffuse toxic goiter (DTG) in the III surgical department of Y. Otabekov's Clinic of Andijan State Medical Institute from 2010 to 2019 with medical history, operative log data, and outpatient cards introduced. When we conducted a retrospective analysis of 263 patients who were discharged from treatment, we found that 120 patients underwent ST examination, of which: 76 patients were found to have up to 1.0 grams of thyroid gland left in the thyroid seat, 30 patients had up to 1.1+2.0 grams of thyroid gland, 14 people had up to 2.1+3.0 grams of thyroid gland. Patients who underwent this ST operation were called group 1.

Out of 263 patients, 1.0-gram gland autograft was implanted in 65 patients after subtotal thyroidectomy. 41 of them had 1.0+2.0 grams of autograft gland tissue planted on the 1.0 grams of gland residue, 13 of them had 1.0+2.0 grams of autograft gland tissue planted on the 1.1+2.0 grams of gland residue, 11 of them had 1.0+2.0 grams of autograft gland tissue planted on the 2.1+3.0 grams of gland residue. We designated these patients who underwent subtotal thyroidectomy as group 2.

In the following 78 patients out of 263 patients, in addition to total thyroidectomy, the gland was isolated from under the gland by tying it with a continuous knot of silk thread, but the gland is not separated from its base. That is, up to +1.0 grams over the node (n=51), up to 1.1+2.0 grams (n=15), up to 2.1+3.0 grams (n=12), the patient was left with a continuous gland seat

untouched. Group 3 (TTAP) was performed together with total thyroidectomy and leaving gland autograft.

When we divided 263 patients who underwent surgery with diffuse toxic goiter between 2010 and 2019 into women and men, 228 (86.7%) were female and 35 (13.3%) were male, with a female-to-male ratio of 7:1. Enlargement of the thyroid gland in the II degree was detected in 19 (7.2%) patients, III-level enlargement was found in 124 (47.1%) patients, IV-level enlargement - in 92 (35%) patients, V-level enlargement - in 28 (10.6%) patients. From the table, it became clear that most of the patients reported with III- and IV-level enlargement.

The methods of the research. Complaints and anamnesis of 263 patients who applied were thoroughly studied, the following examination methods were used.

Clinical objective and subjective examinations were conducted in 263 patients (vision, palpation). Instrumental examinations: ultrasound examination (USE) and electrocardiogram (ECG) were used in 263 patients. Biochemical analysis: checking the amount of "cholesterol" in blood serum was carried out in 242 patients. The amount of total calcium (Ca⁺) in blood serum and urine was examined in 263 patients and determination of phosphorus (R⁺) in 12 patients. Radioimmunological tests: T₃, T₄, TTG, anti-TPO, anti-Tg were examined in 225 patients, parathyroid hormone was examined in 3 patients. Contrast-enhanced computer tomography was performed in 36 patients to examine the front of the neck, behind the tongue, under the spine and behind the sternum. 58 patients with suspected fine needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB) were examined on an outpatient basis. Post-operative histo-pathomorphological examination was conducted in 263 patients.

Statistical analysis. Student's t-criterion was used to evaluate the reliable differences of the Excel program in the WINDOWS_XP environment obtained from the controls. The comparison of the number of groups was checked according to the value of Student's criterion $p < 0,05$, $p < 0,01$, $p < 0,001$.

Results and Discussions. Our ongoing research sheds light on how important the weight of the gland residue is in DTG operations, as well as the amount of gland graft or autoplant being installed, and we analyze the following tables.

After ST, 18 of 35 patients (15%) had an POH (postoperative hypothyroidism) when a gland residue was left up to 1.0 grams, in 12 patients (10%), 1.1-2.0 grams of gland residue was left, in 5 patients (4.2%), 2.1-3.0 grams of gland residue was left.

After STAT 6 of 8 patients (9,2%) had an POH when a gland residue was left up to 1.0 grams, in 2 patients (3,1%) 1,1-2,0 grams of gland residue was left.

After STAT and TTAP, POH was not observed among those with 2.1-3.0 grams of residual gland.

After TTAP 1 of 2 patients (1,3%) had an POH when a gland residue was left up to 1.0 grams, in 1 patient (3,1%) 1,1-2,0 grams of gland residue was left.

When comparing group 2 patients with up to 1.0 grams of glandular tissue to group 1, hypothyroidism was significantly less observed by 3 times ($p < 0.001$). Group 3 was reliably reduced by 6 times compared to group 2 ($p < 0.001$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, hypothyroidism was significantly reduced by 18 times ($p < 0.001$).

When comparing group 2 patients with 1.1-2.0 grams, compared to group 1, hypothyroidism was reliably reduced by 6 times ($p < 0.001$). Group 3 was significantly reduced by

2 times compared to group 2 ($p < 0.01$), and hypothyroidism was significantly reduced by 12 times when group 3 was compared to group 1 ($p < 0.001$).

Hypothyroidism was observed in patients of group 1, who were left up to 2.1-3.0 g, but hypothyroidism was not detected in groups 2 and 3.

When group 2 patients were compared to group 1 by the total weight of the left thyroid gland, hypothyroidism was observed more than 4.4 times less reliably ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, hypothyroidism was significantly reduced by 4-fold ($p < 0.001$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, hypothyroidism was significantly reduced by 18-fold ($p < 0.001$).

After ST, it was detected 5 out of 12 patients (4.2%) had a relapse when the gland residue was up to 1.0 grams, 3 patients (2.5%) had up to 1.1-2.0 grams, 4 patients (3.3%) had up to 2.1-3.0 grams.

After STAT it was observed 1 of 4 patients (1,5%) had a relapse when the gland residue was up to 1.0 grams, 2 patients (3,1%) had up to 1.1-2.0 grams, 1 patient (1,5%) had up to 2.1-3.0 grams.

After TTAR it was recorded 1 of 2 patients (1,3%) had a relapse when the gland residue was up to 1.0 grams, 1 patient (1,3%) had up to 2.1-3.0 grams. After TTAR, there was no relapse among those with 1.1-2.0 grams of gland residue.

When comparing patients of group 2 with up to 1.0 grams of gland residue compared to group 1, relapse was reliably observed 5 times less ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, there was no change, and when group 3 was compared to group 1, relapse was reliably reduced by 5 times ($p < 0.001$).

When comparing group 2 patients with 1.1-2.0 grams compared to group 1, the relapse rate reliably decreased by almost 1.5 times ($p < 0.05$). No relapse was detected in group 3.

When comparing group 2 patients with 2.1-3.0 grams of gland remaining compared to group 1, relapse was reliably observed 4 times less ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, there was no change, and when group 3 was compared to group 1, relapse was reliably reduced by 4 times ($p < 0.001$).

When comparing group 2 patients to group 1 in terms of the total weight of the remaining thyroid gland, relapse was reliably observed 4.4 times less ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, the relapse was reliably reduced by 2-fold ($p < 0.01$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, relapse was reliably reduced by 6-fold ($p < 0.001$).

After ST, it was detected 49 of 73 patients (40,8%) had an euthyrosis when the gland residue was up to 1.0 grams, 15 patients (12,5%) had up to 1,1-2,0 grams, 9 patients (7,5%) had up to 2,1-3,0 grams.

After STAT it was observed 33 of 53 patients (50,8%) had an euthyrosis when the gland residue was up to 1.0 grams, 10 patients (15,4%) had up to 1,1-2,0 grams, 10 patients (15,4%) had up to 2,1-3,0 grams.

After TTAR it was recorded 49 of 74 patients (62,8%) had an euthyrosis when the gland residue was up to 1.0 grams, 14 patients (17,9%) had up to 2,1-3,0 grams, 11 patients (14,1%) had up to 2,1-3,0 grams.

When comparing group 2 patients with up to 1.0 grams of thyroid gland residue to group 1, euthyroidism was reliably observed 1.5 times less ($p < 0.05$). When group 3 was compared to

group 2, it was reliably increased by 1.5 times ($p < 0.05$). When group 3 was compared to group 1, the absolute index of patients in the state of euthyroidism remained unchanged.

When comparing group 2 patients with up to 1.1-2.0 grams of thyroid gland residue to group 1, the state of euthyroidism reliably decreased by 1.5 times ($p < 0.05$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, it reliably increased by 1.5 times ($p < 0.05$), the state of euthyroidism decreased when group 3 was compared to group 1.

When comparing group 2 patients with up to 2.1-3.0 grams of thyroid gland residue to group 1, euthyroidism reliably increased. When group 3 was compared to group 2, the state of euthyroidism increased, and when group 3 was compared to group 1, it increased.

When comparing group 2 patients to group 1 in terms of the total weight of the thyroid gland residue, it was observed euthyroidism was reliably 1.4 times less ($p < 0.05$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, the state of euthyroidism reliably increased by 2 times ($p < 0.05$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, the state of euthyroidism decreased.

Future meta-analyses will certainly play a role in studying the development of postoperative complications. This includes the retrospective reviews we conduct. We have thoroughly studied the period from 2010 to 2019 and obtained the following results.

After ST, it was detected 18 of 35 patients (15%) had POH up to 1 year, 12 (10%) had up to 5 years, and 5 (4.2%) had up to 10 years.

After STAT it was observed 1 of 8 patients (1.5%) had POH up to 1 year, 3 (4.6%) had up to 5 years, 4 (6.2%) had up to 10 years.

After TTAP no POH was observed between the period of 1 year and 5 to 10 years. Between the period of 1 and 5 years, 2 (2.6%) patients had POH.

When group 2 patients were compared to group 1 for the period of 1 year, hypothyroidism was reliably observed 18 times less frequently ($p < 0.001$). No POH was observed in group 3 during the period of 1 year.

When comparing group 2 patients to group 1, hypothyroidism decreased by 4 times ($p < 0.001$). Group 3 was reliably reduced by 1.5 times compared to group 2 ($p < 0.05$), and hypothyroidism was significantly reduced by 6 times when group 3 was compared to group 1 ($p < 0.001$).

Although POH was not detected in group 3 from 5 to 10 years, when group 2 patients were compared to group 1, hypothyroidism decreased in numbers, but increased in percentage.

From 1 to 10 years, comparing group 2 patients to group 1, hypothyroidism was reliably observed 4.4 times less frequently ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, there was a 4-fold reliable reduction in hypothyroidism ($p < 0.001$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, there was a reliable 18-fold reduction in hypothyroidism ($p < 0.001$).

After ST, STAT and TTAP, no relapse was detected in patients within 1 year.

Relapse was observed in 4 out of 12 patients (3.3%) within 5 years after ST, in 8 patients (6.7%) within 10 years. Relapse was detected in 1 out of 4 patients (1.5%) within 1 year after STAT, in 3 patients (4.6%) within 10 years. Relapse was observed in 1 out of 2 patients (1.3%) within 5 years after TTAP, in 1 patient (1.5%) within 10 years.

When comparing group 2 patients to group 1 within a period of up to 5 years, relapse was observed 4 times less reliably ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, there was no change, and when group 3 was compared to group 1, relapse was significantly reduced by 4 times ($p < 0.001$).

In the period from 5 to 10 years, when comparing group 2 patients to group 1, the relapse rate decreased by almost 3 times ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, it was reliably reduced by 3 times ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 1, relapse was significantly reduced by 8 times ($p < 0.001$).

From 1 to 10 years, when comparing group 2 patients to group 1, relapse was reliably observed 3 times less ($p < 0.001$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, the state of relapse was significantly reduced by 2-fold ($p < 0.01$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, the state of relapse was significantly reduced by 6-fold ($p < 0.001$).

After ST it was detected, 8 out of 73 patients (6.7%) had euthyroidism up to 1 year, 26 patients (21.7%) had up to 5 years, 39 patients (32.5%) had up to 10 years.

After STAT, it was observed 8 out of 53 patients (12.3%) had euthyroidism up to 1 year, 20 patients (30.8%) had up to 5 years and patients (38.5%) had up to 10 years.

After TTAP, it was recorded 4 out of 74 patients (5,1%) had euthyroidism up to 1 year, 27 patients (34,6%) had up to 5 years, 43 patients (55,1%) had up to 10 years.

When patients of group 2 were compared to group 1 up to 1 year, euthyroidism remained unchanged in terms of numbers, but a reliable increase of about 2 times was observed in terms of percentages ($p < 0.05$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, it decreased by 2 times, and when group 3 was compared to group 1, the number of patients with euthyroidism was reliably reduced ($p < 0.01$).

When patients of group 2 were compared to group 1 up to 5 years, the numbers in the state of euthyroidism decreased by 1.3 times, but the percentages increased by 1.5 times ($p < 0.05$). When group 3 was compared to group 2, it decreased by 1.3 times ($p < 0.05$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, the number of patients with euthyroidism was reliably reduced.

Until 10 years, when group 2 patients were compared to group 1, euthyroidism decreased by 1.6 times in numbers, but increased by 1.4 times in percentage. When group 3 was compared to group 2, it was reliably increased ($p < 0.05$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, the state of euthyroidism increased.

When comparing the patients of group 2 to group 1 for the period from 1 to 10 years, the absolute indicators of euthyroidism were reliably reduced by about 1.5 times ($p < 0.001$), but the percentage indicators were 1.3 times higher. When group 3 was compared to group 2, euthyroidism was reliably reduced by about 1.5 times ($p < 0.05$), and when group 3 was compared to group 1, euthyroidism was slightly elevated.

Conclusion. Thus, as a result of studying the retrospective analysis of late complications after DTG operations: postoperative hypothyroidism and recurrence, diagnostic-treatment algorithm and surgical tactics were improved in this disease. It is focused on reducing future complications and improving the quality of life of patients with the improved modern surgical treatment method.

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